

for determination of copper. Though less sensitive, the present method is much more selective than dithizone method. Moreover, the present method is very simple and rapid, providing good recovery of copper in presence of most of the common ions. The results are accurate within $\pm 2\%$, rendering the proposed method fairly precise and reproducible. The total operation for each run requires only 10–15 min.

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Estimation of Ethambutal in Pharmaceutical Preparations using some Inorganic Oxidants

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(+)-2,2'-(Ethylenedimino)di-1-butanol dihydrochloride is an orally effective chemotherapeutic agent specially active against the genus mycobacterium including *M. tuberculosis*. In the present work, (+)-2,2'-(ethylenedimino)di-1-butanol dihydrochloride is determined in its various pharmaceutical preparations, viz. using some inorganic oxidants like Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} or V^{V} . The method is highly useful for determining the active ingredient of drug samples accurately without using any complicated procedure and sophisticated instruments. This method is operable at micro sample size, quick and accurate (within $\pm 1\%$ error) as compared to the B.P. method^{1,1}. Results obtained with the present method are compared with the standard method (Table 3).

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) and ammonium metavanadate(V) solutions were prepared in $36 \times 10^{-1} M H_2SO_4$ medium. Potassium hexacyanoferrate solution was standardised iodometrically, and ammonium hexanitratocerate and ammonium metavanadate solutions were standardised by ferrous sulphate or Mohr's salt reagent. All reagents used were of A.R. (B.D.H.) grade. Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) solution could not be prepared in large amount because solution decomposed fairly rapidly. Zinc sulphate was used as catalyst for quantitative oxidation of ethambutol with Fe^{III} in acidic media. Ce^{IV} and V^{V} solutions were stable for several days in acidic medium.

In the preliminary experiments, a known amount of (+)-2,2'-(ethylenedimino)di-1-butanol hydrochloride prepared in distilled water was added to a 10 ml of different molar concentration of Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} or V^{V} reagent in volumetric flask at room temperature (25°). The contents were allowed to react at different intervals of time with occasional shaking. The excess of Fe^{III} was determined with $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ sodium thiosulphate using 10% potassium iodide (5 ml) and starch as an indicator. Excess of Ce^{IV} was determined by $25 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as an indicator and excess of V^{V} was determined by $25 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferrous ammonium sulphate using N-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator (colour rapidly changed from red to green).

Quantitative oxidations of the butanol hydrochloride were not reproducible and non-stoichiometric in various media other than sulphuric acid medium. It is evident from Table 1 that the

TABLE 1—EXTENT OF OXIDATION OF THE BUTANOL HYDROCHLORIDE SAMPLE IN DIFFERENT MOLAR CONCENTRATION OF OXIDANT

	Reagent concentration (M)		
	1×10^{-1}	8×10^{-1}	5×10^{-1}
Fe^{III}			
Time (min)			
10	94.66	95.86	96.22
15	96.42	97.28	98.66
20	97.86	98.22	99.99
25	97.96	98.46	100.21
30	98.22	101.11	104.22
Ce^{IV}			
Time (min)			
10	99.02	101.11	104.22
15	100.12	101.68	101.88
20	100.22	101.72	104.92
25	100.26	100.76	104.94
30	100.28	100.78	104.94
V^{V}			
Time (min)			
10	95.28	96.22	97.82
15	96.98	98.26	101.22
20	97.62	99.01	101.22
25	98.96	100.02	101.86
30	98.98	100.02	101.98

reaction was stoichiometric and reproducible using $5 \times 10^{-1} M$ potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), $1 \times 10^{-1} M$ ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) or $3 \times 10^{-1} M$ ammonium metavanadate reagent within the reaction time of 25 min; the stoichiometry being unaffected by the reversal of the order of the addition of the oxidant and the butanol hydrochloride sample.

Recommended procedure: (+)-2,2'-(Ethylenediamino)di-1-butanol hydrochloride sample (1–5 mg) was allowed to react with the prescribed molar concentration (10 ml) of Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} or V^{V} reagent and allowed to stand for 25 min. The excess of Fe^{III} was then determined by $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ sodium thiosulphate reagent using 10% KI (5 ml) and starch as an indicator. Excess of Ce^{IV} was determined by $25 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferrous ammonium sulphate reagent using ferroin as an indicator, and the excess V^{V} was determined by $25 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferrous ammonium sulphate reagent using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions. Amount of the butanol hydrochloride sample in mg was determined using the following expression.

$$\text{mg of ethambutol sample} = \phi(V_B - V_S)$$

where, $\phi = MN/n$, M being the molecular weight of the butanol hydrochloride sample, N the molarity of the reagent and n the moles of reagent consumed for per mole of the sample, V_B and V_S are the volume of the reagent used for blank and sample experiments, and ϕ is a constant of the reaction having values 0.51, 1.275, 1.275 with Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} and V^{V} reagents, respectively. The results are recorded in Table 2.

The quantitative validity of the oxidation of the butanol hydrochloride with these oxidants is also confirmed by performing recovery experiments

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THE BUTANOL HYDROCHLORIDE SAMPLE WITH INORGANIC OXIDANTS

Taken mg	Found (mg) with		
	$5 \times 10^{-1} M Fe^{III}$	$1 \times 10^{-1} M Ce^{IV}$	$3 \times 10^{-1} M V^{V}$
1.023 5	1 023 3	1.024 7	1.023 8
1.892 6	1 892 2	1.895 0	1.893 1
2.458 6	2.454 8	2.461 8	2.459 2
3.225 6	3.225 2	3.229 4	3.225 9
4.662 8	4.662 2	4.667 8	4.663 7
5.224 0	5 223 6	5.230 5	5.224 9

All results are average of three determinations.

in its pharmaceutical preparations (Table 3). The butanol hydrochloride consume 4 moles of Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} or V^{V} for its oxidation. It may be believed, by considering stoichiometry, that alcoholic group of the compound was oxidised to aldehydic group.

The method is also applicable in presence of excipient normally present in pharmaceutical preparations, and can also be applied for the large amount of drug sample as well.

TABLE 3—RECOVERY EXPERIMENTS

Amount of the butanol hydrochloride sample in each preparation = 200 mg
The pure sample added in each preparation = 5 mg

Preparation Tablet*	Result to analysis in preparation A			Result of preparation + Pure drug added B			Result for pure drug B-A			Percentage recovery			Percentage recovery by B.P. method
	Fe^{III}	Ce^{IV}	V^{V}	Fe^{III}	Ce^{IV}	V^{V}	Fe^{III}	Ce^{IV}	V^{V}	Fe^{III}	Ce^{IV}	V^{V}	
Product-A	201.48	201.56	201.52	206.50	206.55	205.51	5.02	4.99	4.99	100.40	99.80	99.80	100.80
Product-B	200.98	201.66	201.42	205.99	206.66	206.98	5.01	5.00	4.96	100.20	100.10	99.20	99.80
Product-C	201.22	201.88	201.66	206.26	206.92	206.63	5.04	5.04	5.02	100.80	100.80	100.40	100.20
Product-D	200.68	201.42	201.22	205.72	206.43	206.18	5.04	5.01	4.96	100.80	100.20	99.20	100.60
Product-E	201.28	201.68	201.92	206.30	206.65	206.36	5.02	4.97	5.04	100.40	99.40	100.40	99.80
Product-F	200.96	201.22	201.02	205.98	206.19	206.03	5.02	4.97	5.01	100.40	99.40	100.20	99.80
Product-G	201.59	201.86	201.61	206.57	206.89	206.66	4.98	5.03	5.05	99.60	100.65	101.00	100.60
Product-H	200.68	201.02	200.98	205.64	206.00	205.96	4.96	4.98	4.98	99.20	99.60	99.60	99.80
Product-I	199.96	200.68	200.38	204.95	205.67	205.37	4.99	4.99	4.99	99.80	99.80	99.80	100.20
Product-J	200.66	201.22	200.96	205.67	206.27	205.99	5.01	5.05	5.03	100.20	101.00	100.60	100.80
Product K	200.68	200.96	200.72	205.70	205.95	205.72	5.02	4.99	5.00	100.40	99.80	100.00	100.60
Product-L	201.22	201.96	201.66	206.26	206.96	206.65	5.04	5.00	4.99	100.80	100.00	99.80	99.90
Product-M	200.96	201.61	201.22	206.00	206.63	206.23	5.04	5.02	5.01	100.80	100.40	100.20	100.20
Product-N	199.98	200.48	200.12	204.96	205.52	205.16	4.98	5.04	5.04	99.60	100.80	100.80	100.80

* Different commercially available products. All results are average of five experiments.

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